

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF REFLECTION LEVELS IN ADOLESCENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article focused on studying the level of reflexivity in adolescence. In turn, issues related to the manifestation of reflection in adolescence, analyzed by foreign psychologists, are described. At the same time, based on empirical data, the issues of the relationship between the components of reflexivity in adolescence were analyzed.

Keywords: personality, adolescent personality, self-awareness, reflection, past activity, current activity, future activity, cooperation and communication with others, emotionality, success, ability.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ УРОВНЕЙ РЕФЛЕКСИВНОСТИ В ПОДРОСТКОВОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье уделено внимание изучению уровня рефлексивности в подростковом возрасте. В свою очередь, вопросы, связанные с проявлением рефлексии в подростковом возрасте, проанализированы зарубежными психологами. Вместе с тем, на основе эмпирических данных проанализированы вопросы взаимосвязи между компонентами рефлексивности в подростковом возрасте.

Ключевые слова: личность, личность подростка, самосознание, рефлексия, прошлая деятельность, текущая деятельность, будущая деятельность, сотрудничество и общение с другими, эмоциональность, успех, способность.

Adolescence is an active period for the development of self-awareness. And the means of its development is personal reflection. Adolescents deepen their self-study by enriching their self-awareness with new material. They study their personality traits, relationships with others, capabilities and aspirations, strengths and weaknesses. Reflection connects the future and the past, comparing expectations about adult life in childhood. The meaningful plan of reflection is very broad, and the adolescent analyzes the surrounding world, the self-reflection of other people, and their personal reflection. An important feature of reflection is its rich emotionality. Rapidly changing appearance, self-perception with others, successes and abilities in educational activity are always at the center of reflection and generate strong experiences, as a result of which they themselves are reflected.

Another important feature of adolescent reflection is its free association. A teenager is occupied with thoughts coming from different directions under the influence of their mental experiences and external circumstances. However, at the center of reflection is himself, that is, his personality. It is in reflection that he satisfies the need for self-identification, he is most interested in his "I." A teenager tries to understand their "I," finding an answer to the question "Who am I?" is the main problem of this period.

Obviously, reflexive abilities are not the same in all adolescents. The intensity and breadth of reflection in adolescence are directly related to the influence of such factors as family upbringing in childhood, family traditions, reading and discussing good books, paying attention to the thoughts and experiences of other people, and being amazed by the creation of the world. However, a characteristic

feature of all adolescents is that they have the opportunity to raise themselves to a higher level spiritually in a short time granted by nature.

It should be noted that, according to L.I. Bozhovich, during this period, a new stage of self-awareness arises, characterized by the emergence of needs and abilities to understand oneself as a personality with qualities unique to oneself, distinguishing oneself from others. During this period, the adolescent's desire for self-expression and self-education intensifies[1].

Also, L.I. Bozhovich believes that it is the development of reflection in adolescents that leads to a new level of self-awareness. It can be said that in adolescence, reflection develops intensively, which allows it to be studied as a manifestation of its personal characteristics in the processes of self-knowledge (thinking, memory, attention, etc.) in communication with people and behavior.

It is known that A. Buzeman, in his research, based on the opinion of L.S. Vygotsky, notes that there are 3 conditions characterizing the development of reflection in adolescence:

Firstly, reflection and self-awareness based on it are aimed at the development of the adolescent's personality. Self-awareness is considered not only as a phenomenon of awareness, but also in a broader sense as a biologically and socially assimilated variant. According to A. Buzeman, the roots of reflection should be sought deeply in the living world, the biological basis of which is manifested everywhere not only in the reflection of the external world, but also in the reflection of the organism itself.

Secondly, A. Buzeman specifically notes the existence of a connection between the development of adolescent self-awareness and social development. According to him, the development of self-awareness can be connected with the cultural environment, some aspect of his spiritual life.

Thirdly, it calls for attention to the fact that self-awareness is not some kind of metaphysical existence that cannot be analyzed, but that it can influence reflection on the subject as an image that transforms it [9].

In adolescence, a person has a special pleasure in entering their own world, analyzing their thoughts, feelings, and actions.

It should be noted that the following aspects of the problem of studying the psychological characteristics of reflection in adolescents can be clarified:

- the pedagogical aspect is that a high level of reflection in adolescents is one of the necessary conditions for understanding the dynamics of achieving success in their educational activities;

The social aspect is linked to the individual's success in entering a new system of internal (reflexive) and external active social relations. This allows them to prevent potential conflict situations and eliminate communication barriers;

- psychologically, reflection ensures the effectiveness and harmony of personal development, manifested by the adolescent as a form of understanding their inner world [2].

According to L.S. Vygotsky, L.I. Bozhovich, V.I. Slobodchikova, E. Spranger, N.I. Gutkina, S.Yu. Stepanova, and others, reflection is distinguished as renewal in adolescence. This renewal is considered from the point of view of the process of psychological development of the individual. In particular, the child initially realizes himself, imagines himself as a whole person, and develops the ability for self-development.

According to L.S. Vygotsky, reflection is the reflection of processes occurring in the adolescent's consciousness. The development of the emergence of reflection and self-awareness acquires a new principle, that is, internal regulation of mental processes and behavior. The development of reflection in adolescents is not limited to their own internal personal changes; with its emergence, the adolescent understands other people more broadly and deeply [7].

According to E. Erikson, the main task of development before an adolescent is the formation of personal identity, uniqueness, requires a reaction to his thoughts, feelings, and his personality in general, while realizing himself as a person.

It should be noted that personal reflection - on the one hand, as a method of organizing reflexive processes based on the value-spiritual orientation of the adolescent, ensures the creation of his new image, and on the other hand, ensures relationships with the social-objective world, manifested in the assimilation of adequate knowledge about the world.

Yu.M.Linetskiy asserts that personal reflection in adolescence depends on their achieved capabilities and developed reflexive abilities. The main goal of the research process is to study the development of reflexive abilities in adolescents [4].

Researcher P.P. Blonsky also paid special attention to the problem of reflection in adolescence, that is, self-awareness and self-assessment, and tried to explain the problem by connecting it with the level of development of thinking. In his opinion, the development of thinking in adolescence teaches them to control their behavior and intellectual activity.

Issues related to the sense of reflection and its manifestation in the personality of adolescents can also be seen in the research of V.G. Maralov. Researchers define the sense of reflection, manifested in adolescence, as the facet of "self-reflection." When studying it, it is necessary to take into account four main directions, namely cooperation, communication, and personal intellectuality in the activities of adolescents. According to him, reflection is carried out as follows: awareness - focusing one's views on oneself;

- thinking;
- analyzing other knowledge to obtain new knowledge or identify unclear knowledge;
- conscious self-observation;
- self-expression in life activities;
- self-directed analysis by a person, etc. [5].

It is known that, according to L.I. Bozhovich, a new stage of self-awareness arises in adolescence. In this case, the need and abilities arise for the adolescent to understand himself as a personality with distinct characteristics from others. As a result, adolescents develop characteristics such as self-expression and self-affirmation[1].

According to L.I. Bozhovich, the development of reflection in adolescence leads to a new stage of self-awareness. From this point of view, by adolescence, reflection develops rapidly and helps to control cognitive processes (imagination, attention, memory, thinking) and one's personal characteristics. According to A. Buzeman, according to L.S. Vygotsky, there are 3 characteristics that characterize reflection in adolescence:

- firstly, reflection is accompanied by the development of adolescents;
- secondly, they begin to understand themselves. According to A. Buzeman, the roots of reflection go back to the animal world; from the second, self-awareness begins. According to A. Buzeman, the roots of reflection go back to the animal world; self-awareness and social development are interconnected phenomena. In his opinion, self-awareness is directly related to the social environment;
- thirdly, self-awareness is not considered a metaphysical phenomenon. It directly affects the reflection and is directly related to the subject [9].

With the help of reflection, a person begins to develop the experience of controlling their behavior. This is directly related to the process of value thinking. It also helps the individual adapt to external conditions. Most importantly, it also creates conditions for the effective use of other possibilities of the psyche. In adolescence, as a result of immersion in one's own world, a person

derives pleasure from reflecting on their thoughts, feelings, and actions. A teenager performs reflection as a result of relationships and communication with others. In it, an internal dialogue arises regarding the acceptance or rejection of surrounding events and thoughts. He rejects or accepts such opinions and views [6].

Reflection helps to make the process of self-awareness purposeful and conscious.

In the candidate dissertation of T.Yu. Kaminskaya on the topic "The Motivational Component of the "I" Image in the Development of Self-Awareness in Schoolchildren," the role of the motivational component in the development of the "I" image, the management of situation assessment, the influence of personal values on the consciousness of students, and the relationship between goal selection and behavioral styles in adolescents are analyzed. Especially in adolescence, the unity of cognitive and motivational components and age characteristics in the development of the "I" image of behavioral control qualities are highlighted [3].

At the same time, the question of reflection, self-awareness, and its structural components has been studied by a number of researchers. In particular, in the candidate dissertation of N.G. Serkovnikova on the topic "Psychological Features of Moral Self-Awareness of Adolescents in the Process of Adaptation to the Environment," the structural components of moral self-awareness in the individual, the formation of moral self-awareness of adolescents in various environmental conditions, and gender differences in it were investigated. One of the characteristic aspects of the research work is the analysis of the formation of moral self-awareness from the point of view of adolescents with deviant behavior [8].

In conclusion, reflection is of great importance in the life of an adolescent, contributing to self-awareness, self-control, and the development of one's inner world. At the same time, reflection plays an important role in the sociability and social activity of the individual. An adolescent with developed reflection is capable of setting socially significant goals and finding ways to achieve them. In many cases, a person's ability to understand the environment and the ability to recognize social values is important in communication and active life.

It is known that the formation of personality has its own stage of development. In particular, it is characterized by the development of reflexive processes such as self-awareness, self-control, self-management, and self-education. Therefore, in the study, in particular, in order to check the level of development of reflexivity in different age periods, empirical data were collected using the methodology "Determining the Level of Reflexibility" (V.V. Ponamaryov) and the questionnaire "Study of Priority Strategies of Reflexibility."

Initially, this methodology was analyzed separately from the point of view of each age period. The results of the quantitative analysis are reflected in the table.

Table 1

Features of the manifestation of levels of reflexivity in adolescence (according to the Pearson correlation criterion)

Directions of reflexivity	To past activity	Current activity	For future activity	Collaborate and communicate with others
To past activity	1	0,20**	0,05	0,02
Current activity	0,20**	1	0,09	0,12

For future activity	0,05	0,09	1	0,18*
Collaborate and communicate with others	0,01	0,12	0,18*	1

note: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$.

According to the results of the methodology, reflection on current activity with reflection on past activity ($r=0.20$; $p \leq 0.01$) has a high degree of significance. No person can achieve success in their current activities without the knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired in the past. Therefore, the experience of the past plays an invaluable role in the successes achieved in our current activities.

Reflection on future activity has a significant correlation with reflection on cooperation and communication with others ($r=0.18$; $p \leq 0.05$). It is known that the future activity of a person is largely determined by effective interaction with surrounding people and the formation of communication skills.

From the results of the methodology, it can be seen that the development of reflexivity in the personality of adolescents is determined by the development of their communication skills.

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